

MODERN APPROACHES TO STUDYING THE CAUSES OF CLASS DISCIPLINE BY STUDENTS OF GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article discusses the causes of student misbehavior in the classroom and strategies to address them.*

Keywords: *student, teenager, lesson, disciplinary attitude, pedagogical strategy, procedure, manners, behavior, moral-will qualities, moral culture, moral standards, family values.*

During adolescence, many problematic questions related to self-awareness and feelings, desires, and dreams arise in the psyche of boys and girls. ", "how", "who needs it and why". The mental characteristics and functions of the child serve to capture the wonders of the animate and inanimate nature surrounding him through physical and social means [1].

In general, the creation of favorable conditions for the spiritual development of a person depends on how well parents, psychologists and educators understand the laws of learning behavioral norms at one or another age. Overcoming the contradictions between personal desire and the needs of society, between one's own needs and the desires of others, the family is achieved with the help of parents, psychologists and pedagogues [2].

It should be recognized that following the discipline of the lesson is not only the continuous participation of the students in the lessons. If the student regularly participates in the classes and cannot master the educational materials, this situation also indicates a negative attitude towards the discipline of the class. The fact is that the student must come from the family to be mentally and mentally ready for the lesson process, and with the direct participation of the teacher, they must acquire knowledge, skills, skills and competencies at the level of the requirements of the DTS. This requirement is reflected in the Law "On Education". Uniqueness is especially important when working with teenage students. In order to educate a perfect personality, we need not students who sit quietly in the classroom and do not learn educational materials, but on the contrary, students who are active, responsive, have their own thoughts and speech, and can achieve educational efficiency.

Usually, a student who violates discipline understands that his behavior is wrong, but does not understand the motive of such behavior. Each child has different reasons and goals for this behavior. Regardless of what these motives are, educators should choose effective ways to influence them. If pedagogues are able to determine the goals of discipline violations, then they can establish constructive relations with students, and ineffective communication will turn into effective communication. Choosing the right strategy in these actions allows you to find a solution to the problem step by step. The conditions created as a result of pedagogical intervention in such a situation provide certain opportunities for correcting children's discipline.

Discipline is also the ground of learning, and at the same time the result. Already in the middle stage of school, through moral awareness, many important views begin to change,

depending on the moral side of adolescent students. Moral standards, legal standards are requirements that teenagers face every day and adhere to them depending on the level of their education or are strengthened in the form of habits and aspirations [3].

School practice has been collecting various information (pedagogical portfolio) for pedagogues regarding this problem by observing the behavior of students for centuries. Evidence from everyday life expands the problematic aspects of school discipline, while practitioners try to find solutions to the problem (Table 1).

1-table

Strategies to eliminate the cases of violation of discipline in the class of teenage students

Unit of the problem area of school discipline	Solving problems
Violation of school discipline by students	Taking into account the important needs of students - participation in one or another socially important process or membership in groups. Helping students choose the types of ethics that are convenient to meet these needs.
The student's behavior is aimed at paying attention to himself.	Adhering to the rules of paying attention to students, paying attention by looking into his eyes during the lesson, repeating his name several times while explaining the subject of the lesson, warning him in writing. Unexpected situations: turning off the lights, speaking in a low voice, speaking to the music, changing the voice, talking to the wall or a portrait, temporarily stopping the lesson, asking students questions, changing their place, drawing the attention of the class to an example of good behavior focus etc.
Passing his judgment (the student behaves "badly" because it is important for him to be first and he wants to impose judgment on the teacher, the whole class)	Avoiding confrontation and not acting abruptly, giving the student some freedom, "dominating".
Behavioral characteristics such as "revenge" (the main goal for the student is to take revenge on a teacher or student for "hurt" that he invented or caused will remain.)	Caution is required in this situation. Acknowledge the student's "dominance", do not discuss the situation in front of the class, take notes, agree with the student, change the subject, remove the student: out of the classroom, to the school administration room, make demands on him: exclude him from his favorite activity, communication with his friends, go to the school principal's room, meet his parents, compensate for the damage he caused, demand to fix what he broke or damaged, etc.

<p>Hostile situation with the student</p>	<p>Paying attention to the behavior of the student, not to his personality; do not allow negative emotions to appear (do not shout, "I am the teacher here for now", do not say insulting words that humiliate the student, do not use sarcasm, do not use physical force, do not insist that I am right, this not to involve others in the conflict, not to give advice, not to compare the student with others, etc.</p> <p>• To discuss this situation later, not to spoil his reputation in front of other students.</p>
<p>Sleeping in classes</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discuss the reasons for this situation with the student (family environment, long hours of work, computer games, etc.). Advice on how to allocate time. 2. Tell us about diseases that cause regular sleepiness. Offer to monitor his symptoms over a period of time. 3. Be positive about such students. Maybe they know why but don't want to tell you. 4. If your previous efforts do not help, try to talk about it with the parents, because they can provide an opportunity for the child to rest at home if necessary.
<p>1. Use of irregular lexical expressions. (the student uses various non-standard lexical expressions so that the teacher and adults do not hear him)</p> <p>2. Intentional use of non-standard lexical expressions (insult and humiliation of the teacher by the student)</p>	<p>Discuss this situation at the beginning of the year. Explain to the student why such expressions are unpleasant for others, and it is necessary to speak in the language generally accepted at school. Ask him to find other ways to break this bad habit. In order to get rid of these harmful habits, clarify what the student should do in the sequence.</p> <p>If you hear a student saying something inappropriate, never ask, "What did you say?" By doing this, you will make him repeat these words again. Explain to the teen that he is wrong and that he is wrong. It should also be taken into account that the student may be very emotional in his work and may say such words involuntarily.</p> <p>Don't accept the reader's explanation that he meant something else when he said these words. In many cases, the student rushes to apologize when he says these words accidentally. You should not punish him because he admitted his guilt and promised to correct his mistake. If this continues, the above measures must be taken by the teacher. It is important that the teacher himself tries not to use such words during the lesson, because the teacher should always be an example for students in everything.</p> <p>If the student is unable to control himself, report this to the school principal immediately and request a</p>

	meeting with the parent. If the student's behavior has not affected the classroom environment, leave it until the end of the day to notify the administration. Discuss the situation with the student after the lesson. Inform the parents about this situation and explain that the school administration knows about it.
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The best way to maintain discipline in the classroom is to gain the trust of the students. The purpose of the lesson is to make the lesson lively, creative, and with the help of visual aids, to arouse their interest and amazement, and not to leave a single student "beish" at the end of the lesson - to give each of them unique practical tasks.

Being disciplined is important not only in school, but also in the future life of the student. Because discipline is important even in the tangled and complicated paths of human life [4]. Regardless of what strategy is used to improve discipline, it provides an opportunity to constantly monitor and evaluate the activities of students who have a negative attitude to discipline, and to carry out educational corrections. If the undisciplined student is changing for the better, the supervision will continue until he is completely free of negative behavior. In order to motivate the student, it is also useful to occasionally acknowledge that they are making positive changes. The above-mentioned various methods and methods can give the expected effect and result only after studying and analyzing the student's personality, his capabilities and personal plans, social conditions and, most importantly, the motives of indiscipline.

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